

CiROCCO system architecture design and technical specifications

D2.3

CiROCCO

Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts

Consortium

1	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS)
2	Ethniko Asteroskopeio Athinon (NOA)
3	eBOS Technologies Limited (EBOS)
4	Netcompany-Intrasoft SA (INTRA)
5	InoSens doo Novi Sad (INO)
6	Astrocast SA (ASTRO)
7	Centre for Environment and Development for the Arab Region and Europe (CEDARE)
8	University of Cyprus (UCY)
9	Idalion Municipality (DIMOS)
10	Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance (MOL)
11	Public Enterprise "Vojvodinašume" Petrovaradin (VSUME)
12	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC)

Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Type of deliverable	R – Document, report
Work package	WP2 – Interactive Definition of User-oriented Requirements
Deliverable number, title	D2.3 CiROCCO system architecture design and technical specifications
Status - version, date	Finsl - V1.0, 02/09/2024
Deliverable leader	INTRA
Contributing partners	EBOS, NOA, UCY, and others
Contractual date of delivery	31/08/2024
Keywords	System architecture, specifications, interconnections matrix,

Quality Control

	Name	Organisation	Date
Peer review 1	Marios Vlachos	ICCS	28/08/2024
Peer review 2	Kleanthis Erotokritou	EBOS	27/08/2024

Version History

Version	Date	Authors	Organisation	Summary of changes
V0.0	15.05.2024	Marina Georgiou	INTRA	Template
V0.2	15.05.2024	Ilias Romas Marina Georgiou	INTRA	ToC
V0.3	17.07.2024	Kleanthis Erotokritou Marios Sophocleous	UCY	Input for the CiROCCO system components and use cases
		Eleni Drakaki Georgios Grivas Panagiotis Kosmopoulos	NOA	
		Marina Georgiou Ilias Romas	INTRA	
		Mehrdad Ghanad	ASTRO	
		Hesham El-Askary Omar Elbadawy	CEDARE	
		Giorgos Alexandrou Petros Mouzourides	UCY	
V0.4	03.08.2024	Ilias Romas Marina Georgiou	INTRA	Consolidated document
V0.5	28.09.2024	Chrysoula Panathanasiou Kleanthis Erotokritou Marios Sophocleous	ICCS, EBOS	Internal review and plagiarism check
V0.6	31.08.2024	Marina Georgiou Ilias Romas	INTRA	Revised document
V1.0	02.09.2024	Kleanthis Erotokritou	EBOS	Quality Assurance

Legal Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the following information. The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that it is fit for any specific purpose. The CiROCCO project Consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law.

Copyright © CiROCCO Consortium, 2024

Table of contents

Consortium	2
Quality Control.....	3
Version History	3
Legal Disclaimer	4
List of Figures	7
List of Tables	8
List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	9
Executive Summary	11
H1 Goal / Objectives	11
H2 Methodology	11
H3 Outcomes / Conclusions.....	11
1. Introduction	13
1.1. Deliverable description.....	13
1.2. Purpose of the Deliverable	13
1.3. Intended Audience	13
1.4. Deliverable Structure and its Relation with Other Work Packages / Deliverables	13
2. CiROCCO system concept design	16
2.1. System requirements	16
2.2. System architecture design methodology.....	18
2.3. Architectural views and perspectives.....	18
3. CiROCCO system logical viewpoint	20
3.1. Architectural layers	20
3.2. Logical diagram.....	20
3.3. CiROCCO system components and technical specifications	22
3.3.1. In-situ measurement technologies.....	22
3.3.2. Aerosol data assimilation	34
3.3.3. Data stream transfer, management and visualisation	37
3.3.4. CiROCCO pilot systems	44
4. Process viewpoint of the platform	55

4.1.	Interconnections between system components.....	55
4.2.	Pilot 1 Renewable energy systems planning in Egypt	57
4.3.	Pilot 2 Desert dust storm events monitoring in Cyprus	57
4.4.	Pilot 3 Sustainable environmental restoration support in Serbia	59
4.5.	Pilot 4 Modelling greenhouse gases (GHG) and particle emissions in Spain	60
5.	CiROCCO system deployment viewpoint	62
6.	Conclusions	67
7.	References	68

List of Figures

Figure 1: 4+1 view model of system architecture ().....	19
Figure 2: CiROCCO system logical diagram	21
Figure 3: High-level architecture of the LCSNs.....	23
Figure 4: Flowchart of the aerosol data assimilation procedure.	35
Figure 5: Pictorial diagram of the operation of ASTRO's nanosatellite IoT network	38
Figure 6 : Pictorial diagram of INTRA's data streaming and management platform	40
Figure 7: CiROCCO visualisation service's components	42
Figure 8: Pictorial diagram of the energy production nowcasting and forecasting component structure	45
Figure 9: CiROCCO DDS early warning system architecture design	47
Figure 10: Land use and ecosystem management system structure	51
Figure 11: Sequence diagram for pilot 1 in Egypt	57
Figure 12: Data flow for the DDS early warning system	58
Figure 13: Sequence diagram for pilot 2 in Cyprus	59
Figure 14: Sequence diagram for Pilot 3 in Serbia	60
Figure 15: Sequence diagram for Pilot 4 in Spain	61
Figure 16: CiROCCO's system deployment diagram.....	62
Figure 17: Deployment diagram for Pilot 1 in Egypt.....	63
Figure 18: Deployment diagram for Pilot 2 in Cyprus	64
Figure 19: Deployment diagram for Pilot 3 in Serbia	65
Figure 20: Deployment diagram for Pilot 4 in Spain	66

List of Tables

Table 1: CiROCCO system requirements	16
Table 2: Functional requirements	16
Table 3: Non-functional requirements	18
Table 4: Low-cost, in-situ sensing nodes	22
Table 5: Medium-cost sensor nodes	25
Table 6: Portable sunphotometers	28
Table 7: High-end instrument for reference PM monitoring	31
Table 8: Aerosol data assimilation component	34
Table 9: Nanosatellite IoT network	37
Table 10: Data streaming and management platform	39
Table 11: Data visualisation service	42
Table 12: Solar energy production nowcasting and forecasting	44
Table 13: Desert Dust Storm (DDS) early warning system	46
Table 14: Land use and ecosystem management system	50
Table 15: Modelling GHG exchanges and PM emissions	53
Table 16: Interconnections between system's components.	56

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ADA	Data assimilation component
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AERONET	Aerosol Robotic Network
AOD	Aerosol Optical Depth
API	Application Programming Interface
ASIC	Application Specific Integrated Circuit
CALIPSO	Cloud-Aerosol Lidar and Infrared Pathfinder Satellite Observations
CEA	Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives
CNES	Centre national d'études spatiales
COTS	Commercial Off-The Shelf
DDS	Desert Dust Storm
DoA	Description of Action
EARLINET	European Aerosol Research Lidar Network
EC	European Commission
EO	Earth Observation
EWS	Early Warning System
EXT	External data source
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSM	Global System for Mobile communications
HTTPS	Hypertext transfer protocol secure
IoT	Internet of Things
ISM	In-situ monitoring

LCSN	Low-cost sensing node
LEO	Low Earth Orbit
LoRA	Long Range
LTE	Long Term Evolution
LIVAS	Lidar climatology of Vertical Aerosol Structure for space-based lidar simulation studies
MIDAS	Modis Dust Aerosol
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSN	Monitoring Sensing Node
NASA	National Aeronautics Space Administration
OAuth	Open Authorisation
PHOTONS	Photométrie pour le Traitement Opérationnel de Normalisation Satellitaire
PM	Particulate Matter
PL	Pilot
REA	Research Executive Agency
STMV	Stream Transfer, Management and Visualisation
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UART	Universal Asynchronous Receiver/Transmitter
UI	User Interface
USB	Universal Serial Bus
Wi-Fi	Wireless Fidelity

Executive Summary

This deliverable offers an overview of the CiROCCO system architecture, focusing on the architecture design of the CiROCCO system in terms of system-as-a-whole. The system-level technical specifications comprise a high-level view of the layers and components, as well as applications and services. The interaction patterns, the integration points, the interconnection scheme, and the interfaces for exchanging information among them are also presented. Each component is further decomposed into high-level blocks that offer the basis for subsequent detailed description of each component's specifications.

H1 Goal / Objectives

Among the main objectives of this deliverable is to report on work that has been carried out in WP2 | Interactive definition of user-oriented requirements and in particular Task 2.3 | System architecture design and technical specifications and towards the fulfilment of Milestone 7 | Project mid-term and final system architecture in place. Its main goal is that the outcomes of this work are made visible to all the CiROCCO project partners to drive the continuation of technical tasks in WP3 | Tested and validated new in-situ measurement technologies. The CiROCCO system architecture framework will serve as a guide for its deployment and the joint exploitation of the system that will be aligned with the market needs. For this purpose, this report will be maintained as a living document that will be revised over the course of the CiROCCO project to account for updates of the system architecture as well as of the system components.

H2 Methodology

The CiROCCO system architecture framework is based on the 4+1 architectural view model and offers a concise and structured way to visualise and communicate different aspects of the system. The 4+1 viewpoints of the architectural model provide a strong foundation for managing the project's design and making sure that it meets the requirements of all parties (end-users, stakeholders, technical partners) involved when starting with the development of a complex project, such as the CiROCCO system development. An agile approach was selected with three iterations to collect system requirements that drove the design of the architecture framework. After identifying the fundamental functional and non-functional requirements for the CiROCCO system, the definition of the overall architecture framework for the CiROCCO system followed. It consists of five major architectural layers, each one of which consists of several internal components and building blocks with purpose and role as described in the sections of this document.

H3 Outcomes / Conclusions

This deliverable synthesises deliverable D2.1 | Key stakeholders mapping and functional requirements elicitation and analysis and D2.2 | Pilot's requirements, dimensions and target KPIs into a comprehensive system description. This is clearly laid out, and Section 3 of the document, in particular, provides a high-level functional description of the CiROCCO system. Nonetheless, no business (meta)model is presented despite the aim to facilitate such developments. In other words, there is no consideration of the functional and technical role of external entities, such as local authorities.

Key outcomes in bullet points

- CiROCCO system reference architecture
- Harmonised architectural framework with requirements received from WP2 | Interactive definition of user-oriented requirements and input from WP4 | Pilots for improved geographical coverage and impact assessment
- Comprehensive description of CiROCCO system components
- CiROCCO system from a logical viewpoint, process viewpoint, and deployment viewpoint
- Verification of the system components as specified for the use case pilots.

1. Introduction

1.1. Deliverable description

This document provides an overview of the CiROCCO system architecture as it has been defined within the framework of Task 2.3 | System architecture design and technical specifications, as per the DoA of the CiROCCO project. For the design of the CiROCCO system architecture and specifically for the collection of user and technical requirements, we relied on the outcomes of Task 2.1 | Stakeholder Mapping and End-user Needs Analysis through Processes of Co-creation and Task 2.2 | Pilot Requirements and Specifications for Hard-to-Reach Under-sampled Areas.

1.2. Purpose of the Deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is to describe in detail the refined specifications of the reference architecture for the CiROCCO system, which is grounded on a thorough understanding of the underlying technologies, as well as the end-users' and stakeholders' requirements. In this document, each CiROCCO system component is defined in terms of its purpose, functionality, input and output data, dependencies among each other, connecting the components together in the CiROCCO system. Three different viewpoints of the CiROCCO system are specified for each pilot area by: (i) defining the interconnections, points of communication and interfaces between the components in each specific use case; and by (ii) defining data flow specifications. The CiROCCO system's customisation for the different use case pilots and architectural framework deployments are also specified.

1.3. Intended Audience

This deliverable will be made publicly available and accessible through the CiROCCO project website and CORDIS once approved by the European Research Executive Agency (REA) under the powers delegated by the European Commission (EC). The contents of the document aim to guide the CiROCCO project partners towards the development, integration and deployment of the CiROCCO system and its components. Similarly, it can be used as an introductory document guiding future users of the CiROCCO system. Lastly, readers may use it as a reference document beyond the CiROCCO consortium developing similar systems or constituting subsystems and components.

1.4. Deliverable Structure and its Relation with Other Work Packages / Deliverables

This document is organised in six sections as follows:

- **Section 1** is an introductory section providing a general overview of the document.
- **Section 2** presents the methodological approach adopted for the design of the CiROCCO system architectural framework. Individual methodological undertakings are described together with explanations of how they complement each other for a coherent and structured approach.

- In the following **Section 3**, the system components are also presented and, in the subsections, information related to their internal architecture, technologies, TRL, and further details is provided.
- A brief description of each use case pilot of the CiROCCO system is presented in **Section 4**. These updated versions of the descriptions, included in the DoA, were defined in the project's first months and reflect the current needs for the CiROCCO system in each pilot area. These needs have been considered during the definition of the interconnections between the CiROCCO system components, process flows supported by use case as well as sequence diagrams.
- Building upon the conceptual architecture, **Section 5** presents the physical architecture of the CiROCCO system in the form of diagrams which depict all the system's hardware and software components for deployment.
- **Section 6** concludes the deliverable with a summary of main achievements from the work carried out as part of Task 2.3 | System architecture design and technical specifications.

As per the DoA of the CiROCCO project, this report represents the outcome of Task 2.3 | System architecture design and technical specifications of WP2 | Interactive definition of user-oriented requirements. The components that constitute the CiROCCO system architecture are developed in the context of Work Package (WP3) | Tested and validated new in-situ measurement technologies and WP4 | Pilots for improved geographical coverage and impact assessment and specifically, within the following tasks:

WP3	Tested and validated new in-situ measurement technologies
T3.1	Development of low-cost in-situ sensing nodes
T3.2	Development of wireless high-density sensor network
T3.3	Data pre-processing and synchronisation of different accuracy sensing nodes
T3.4	Satellite modelling and assimilation algorithm with the in-situ sensors
T3.5	Data integration and data management platform

WP4	Pilots for improved geographical coverage and impact assessment
T4.2	Renewable energy systems planning
T4.3	Desert dust storm events monitoring
T4.4	Sustainable environmental restoration support
T4.5	Modelling of greenhouse gases and particle emissions

The document builds upon the work and outputs of the afore-mentioned tasks, as presented in the following deliverables of WP2 and WP4:

- key stakeholders' needs and requirements that can be supported by the CiROCCO project activities and have been identified to have added value to the project documented in deliverable **D2.1** | Key stakeholders mapping and functional requirements elicitation and analysis;
- initial (non-)functional requirements, key performance indicators (KPIs) and target values from deliverable **D2.2** | Pilot's requirements, dimensions and target KPIs, as guidance for the functionalities that the CiROCCO system should have;
- the strategy adopted for testing the CiROCCO system and achieving the KPIs as described in **D4.1** | Planning and setup handbook, operational management report – initial.

2. CiROCCO system concept design

2.1. System requirements

The main content of deliverable D2.3 is the design of a clear and robust architecture for the CiROCCO system. To achieve the expected results, it is more than necessary to understand that the analysis performed in the context of D2.1 and D2.2 is the guide to achieve them. In the context of D2.1, an initial analysis of the system was done, and the common features of the system among all pilots were identified. Table 1 below presents these requirements.

Table 1: CiROCCO system requirements

Common system features and requirements
Recording of meteorological and air quality parameters with low-cost sensing nodes
Provision of robust external connectivity options for communication with a cloud server and other sensor networks
Offering a dedicated dashboard for real-time monitoring, data analysis, and customisable alerts
Developing a high-quality system for enhanced accuracy in measurement recording
Enabling remote control and monitoring of nodes with automated and manual options
Low maintenance equipment with reliable and accurate measures
Facilitating maintenance and sensor replacement by personnel without specialised skills

Deliverable D2.2 took the output of D2.1 and expanded the common functional and non-functional requirements for each project pilot through analysis. Functional requirements define what a system must do, while non-functional requirements describe the general properties of the system. Both types of requirements gathered from the four pilot cases of the CiROCCO project are detailed in the consolidated Table 2 found below.

Table 2: Functional requirements

No.	Description	Priority
1	Stand-alone electronic sensing nodes	High
2	Low-cost sensing nodes to record solar radiation	High
3	The low-cost sensing nodes should record meteorological parameters such as air temperature, atmospheric pressure, air humidity, sand / soil temperature, wind direction, wind speed, and solar radiation.	High
4	In-situ stations recording soil characteristics at the source	Low

5	Low-cost sensing nodes to record air quality parameters and specifically, CO ₂ , CO, NO _x , O ₃ , PM ₁ , PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ .	High
6	The low-cost sensing nodes additionally sample total (bulk) dust amount (all fractions) for its chemistry analysis over weekly intervals	Low
7	The temporal resolution will be one sample per hour for the low-cost sensing nodes.	Medium
8	Sensing nodes able to communicate with a cloud server via external connectivity (e.g. Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi), LoRaWAN and satellite communications)	High
9	Sensor nodes to be tested and evaluated in natural environmental conditions, before their operational use	High
10	Sensing nodes to be monitored remotely, automatically, or manually via a control application	Medium
11	At least one higher-quality system to be incorporated in the CiROCCO system	High
12	Installation of two higher quality systems at two sites more than 100 km apart	High
13	The higher-quality components of the CiROCCO system should be able to record the same parameters as the low-cost sensing nodes but with higher accuracy.	High
14	Sensing nodes should be easy and quick to relocate.	Medium
15	The system's design should allow for seamless integration of one or two additional sensors in the future.	Medium
16	The system's design should enable non-specialised personnel to replace individual sensors easily.	Low
17	Data collected should be transmitted through StreamHandler to the data management platform at least every 12 hours.	High
18	Data should be monitored with a sampling rate of at least six measurements per hour, ideally with one measurement every minute.	High
19	The features or databases of the CiROCCO system should be accessible and compatible through an Android and iOS app.	Medium
20	Sensor information to be accessed by registered users of the data management platform with different levels of authorisation	High
21	A dedicated dashboard should provide monitoring information, information on atmospheric and other system conditions, statistics on data collected, and configurable notifications.	High
22	The sensors and/or the receiving systems should have a fault alert function, namely promptly sent notifications about equipment faults, missing data, unexpected outliers and other predefined anomalies in the data.	Low
23	Features or databases of the CiROCCO system should be accessible and compatible with the Early Warning System (EWS) that will be based on an Android app.	Medium

Table 3: Non-functional requirements

No.	Description	Priority
1	Sensing nodes must respect security and privacy requirements.	High
2	Sensing nodes should comply with Conformité Européene (CE) certification standards before they reach the market.	High
6	The nodes' system should be built with robust materials and components, able to withstand diverse weather conditions (rain, high winds, extreme temperatures), ensuring long-term outdoor functionality) with particular emphasis on mitigating fire hazards (e.g. batteries resistant to extreme heat, up to 60°C).	High
4	The nodes' system should achieve energy autonomy 24/7, independent of a fixed power supply source.	Medium
5	The new system's architecture considers the need for sustainability and the principle of zero negative environmental impacts.	High
7	The system should achieve a minimum data-recording autonomy of at least 120 hours (or more), independent of the possible (periodical) manual data recording.	High
8	Training should be provided on the installation, use and maintenance of each piece of equipment and the system in general.	High

2.2. System architecture design methodology

Since requirements describe the problem, the architecture outlines the high-level solution. The functional and non-functional requirements support the development of a clear understanding of the needs that the system will be asked to fulfill and possible constraints, guiding the overall architectural strategy. The CiROCCO system architecture design methodology is based on the well-established 4+1 view model of software architecture, developed by Kruchten (1995) and provides a direct and structured way to address the complexity of software architecture by organising the design into 5 views, each one of which addresses different perspectives of stakeholders. By leveraging the 4+1 model views, the methodology adopted for the design of the CiROCCO system ensures that the architecture is well-documented, maintainable, and able to meet both functional and non-functional requirements.

2.3. Architectural views and perspectives

Each view addresses specific concerns and provides a comprehensive understanding of the system from different perspectives as described below:

Logical view: The logical view is one of the main components of the 4+1 view model. It provides a clear representation of the system and its key components, their relationships, and features. It focuses on the functionalities of the system, and provides a framework for stakeholders, architects and developers to have a clear understanding of the system.

Process view: The process view deals with the dynamic aspects of the system, focusing on processes and their interactions. It is essential for ensuring the system's concurrency, communication, scalability

and performance. The most common way to depict the process view is with activity or state diagrams. These diagrams can illustrate the interactions between components and model the flow between system's events.

Physical view: The physical view is related to the system's deployment architecture. It defines how the software components are mapped to the hardware and network infrastructure (e.g. servers, network devices, etc.). The physical view is mostly presented by deployment diagrams.

Development view: The development view emphasises how the system is organised and managed from a developer's perspective. This view is crucial for ensuring efficient development, maintainability, and reusability of the system's modules. It can be achieved using component diagrams or package diagrams. It facilitates collaboration among development team members by defining clear boundaries and responsibilities for different parts of the system.

+1 scenarios (Use cases): The scenarios or use case view involves use case diagrams and sequence diagrams to validate and connect all other views. Scenarios are crucial for building test cases, validating system behaviour against user expectations and ensuring that the architecture supports the required functionality and user interactions.

Figure 1: 4+1 view model of system architecture

As depicted in Figure 1, the 4+1 model reduces the overall complexity of the system architecture by breaking it down into views, each one of which is focused on a specific aspect (logical functionality, process flow, physical deployment, development organisation, and use case considerations) that makes the system easier to be understood, analysed, and modified. Moreover, the 4+1 view model is flexible and not tied to any specific design tool or language, enabling teams to use tools they are familiar with.

3. CiROCCO system logical viewpoint

In this section, the CiROCCO system layers and components specifications are presented and analysed. Specifically, the components are presented in subsection 3.3, providing information related to their inner architecture, TRL, technology stack, and further details.

3.1. Architectural layers

The development of complex systems such as the CiROCCO system depends heavily on its architecture. One of the most common and widely used architecture patterns is the layered architecture pattern, also known as the n-tier architecture pattern. The most important perhaps feature of the layered architecture pattern is the *separation of concerns* among components that supports modularity and thus flexibility in the development of systems. Each layer of this architecture pattern has a specific role within the system. Components within a specific layer deal only with logic that pertains to that layer.

For the CiROCCO system architecture, the following five layers have been defined following consultation with project partners involved in the development of the system's components and the deployment in the four pilot areas. Specifically, the following layers have been defined:

- **Presentation layer**
 The presentation layer is responsible for handling user requests and displaying the User Interface (UI). It should include applications, dashboards, UI, and Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) that enable the user to interact with the system.
- **Service layer**
 The service layer acts like a bridge between the presentation layer and the data layer. It handles the user requests, as well as the data transformation from the data layer to create valuable output based on the business logic of the application.
- **Data layer**
 This is the layer responsible for the storage of data and the communication with the system databases.
- **Communication layer**
 This layer supports the connectivity among remote devices as well as data exchange between applications of the system.
- **Physical layer**
 This last layer may be considered as the “bottom” layer of the system. It includes the sensors and the smart devices that collect information from the surroundings in the CiROCCO pilot sites.

3.2. Logical diagram

Figure 2 shows the overall logical view of the CiROCCO system architecture. The architecture is presented in a layered pattern, with five vertical and horizontal layers, described earlier in Section 3.2.1. Each layer contains the component being developed for the CiROCCO platform. The grey boxes represent the external components of the CiROCCO system, such as external databases and services.

The pilots, as external services connected to the CiROCCO system, act as examples demonstrating the CiROCCO system’s modularity and ease of connectivity.

Figure 2: CiROCCO system logical diagram

3.3. CiROCCO system components and technical specifications

The CiROCCO system components are presented in the following subsections, which provide information related to their inner architecture, TRL, technologies, and other details.

3.3.1. In-situ measurement technologies

Table 4: Low-cost, in-situ sensing nodes

Component: Low-cost, in-situ sensing nodes
ID: ISM-1
<p>Purpose:</p> <p>The primary purpose of developing the low-cost sensing nodes (LCSNs) is to create an optimised technological solution for gathering crucial environmental data to enhance the modelling of dust cycles and trajectories. The sensing nodes were constructed using readily available (Commercial Off-The-Shelve – COTS) components and designed to withstand harsh environmental conditions of remote pilot sites.</p> <p>Designed as stand-alone devices, these nodes utilise energy harvesting technologies such as photovoltaic cells, vibrations, or miniaturised wind turbines to ensure longevity in harsh conditions without relying on external power sources. Additionally, the sensing nodes feature multiple wireless communication technologies to establish a wireless sensor network and support over-the-air software upgrades, ensuring system flexibility and adaptability.</p>
<p>Description:</p> <p>To ensure prolonged operation without light, the energy harvesting module of LCSNs features a high-capacity photovoltaic cell paired with long-lasting batteries, enabling the system to function for more than two weeks. The intelligent control module houses an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-compatible microcontroller, capable of performing on-the-node processing at exceptionally low power consumption.</p> <p>The packaging of this integrated node is unique and tailored to withstand harsh environments while ensuring accurate and timely data measurements. To suit the pilot requirements, a data transmission module has been developed to enable wireless transmission using Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, Long Range (LoRa) and Long-Term Evolution (LTE)/5G whenever feasible. When necessary, data retrieval from the edge devices is facilitated through ASTRO's nanosatellite network, offering satellite communication services. Figure 3 illustrates the high-level architecture of the LCSNs.</p>

Figure 3: High-level architecture of the LCSNs

The LCSNs are equipped with a range of miniaturised sensors to measure a wide range of environmental parameters, including temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, wind direction, solar radiation, and atmospheric pollutants, such as PM (PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀) and CO₂. The measurements collected could be categorised into the following:

Air quality measurements carried out using a Sensirion SCD41-D-R2 which measures CO₂ concentrations and an Alphasense OPC-R2 sensor which measures PM₁, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁₀ concentrations. **Note:** The LCSN was initially equipped with NO₂ and Ozone sensors. However, given the system's functional requirements, a CO₂ was prioritised over the NO₂ and Ozone sensors for measuring CO₂ concentrations. This change aligned better with the project needs and contributed to keeping the LCSN within budget constraints.

Meteorological measurements are collected using a BME688 sensor which measures air temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, and gas resistance, an HWA042 sensor which measures sand / soil temperature and water content, an ultrasonic anemometer, and a Renke solar radiation sensor which captures wind direction and speed and solar radiation.

Starting TRL:

5

Expected TRL:

8

Technology stack:

for measurements:

- recording of air quality parameters (PM₁, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀)
- recording of meteorological parameters (air temperature, atmospheric pressure, air humidity, soil humidity, sand/soil temperature, wind direction, wind speed, solar radiation)
- recording of additional air quality parameters (CO₂, CO)

for the device's operation:

-
- microcontroller unit
 - power management module, including power supply for the system intelligence board and solar charging of lead-acid battery via a buck-boost converter, achieving net zero emission target.

for data transmission:

- internal communication modules: Wi-Fi and Bluetooth embedded in the microcontroller unit
- external communication modules with the cloud server: LoRaWAN, LTE, and satellite communications, all interfaced with the ESP32.

for user interaction with the device

- remote management, achievable via multiple communication modules.

Dependencies with other components:

The LCSNs can use satellite Internet of Things (IoT) via the Astronode S module provided by ASTRO, which is extremely useful in regions without LTE / 5G or Wi-Fi coverage.

Requirements:

Autonomy & self-containment:

LCSNs have been designed and developed and are currently undergoing testing as stand-alone electronic sensing nodes with energy autonomy for at least two weeks.

Availability:

LCSNs will be operating continuously once installed and until the end of the CiROCCO project or a 2-year period for which evaluation and re-calibration measurements will be available from medium-cost and high-end sensing nodes.

Resolution:

LCSNs will provide data at a resolution of 30 minutes or 1 hour, depending on the energy autonomy aiming to achieve.

Monitoring:

Sensing nodes will be monitored remotely, automatically, or manually via the control application. Both sensors and data receiving systems have a fault alert function for promptly notifying about equipment faults, missing data, unexpected outliers, and other predefined anomalies in the collected data.

Extensibility & Scalability:

The LCSN modular design supports adding sensors to / inside the sensor casing. Additional sensors can be integrated via RS485 or General-Purpose Input / Output (GPIO).

Portability:

Although portable, since they weight approximately 6 kg and have dimensions of 23 x 32 x 19 cm, LCSNs are designed to be installed permanently at selected locations in the pilot areas and collect stationary measurements. Nonetheless, LCSNs are designed for easy and quick relocation as they are powered by a battery and support internationally accepted communication protocols. Assembly

and installation guidance is provided in a detailed step-by-step guidebook, while training material is prepared for their use, and maintenance.

Deployment:

All four pilot site locations

Relevant WP:

WP3

Tasks:

T3.1

Deliverables:

D3.1 and D3.2

Involved partners:

EBOS

Table 5: Medium-cost sensor nodes

<p>Component: Medium-cost sensor nodes</p>
<p>ID: ISM-2</p>
<p>Purpose: Medium-cost, sensor-based, air quality monitoring systems or Monitoring Sensor Nodes (MSNs), which are priced between € 3,000 - 15,000, are increasingly being used for air quality monitoring and pollutant emissions mitigation. In situ measurements of air pollutant concentrations is the most crucial stage of integrated air quality management, which includes inter alia providing support for population exposure assessment, early warning systems for the public and stakeholders, and evaluation of atmospheric and satellite modelling products. In the framework of CiROCCO project, the utilisation of commercial, multi-pollutant systems for air quality monitoring will supplement the networks of LCSNs, gauging the reliability of their measurements and providing inputs to algorithms for the improvement of LCSN data outputs. The systems will monitor PM parameters (i.e. PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, PM₁) that will also be captured by the LCSNs, additional regulated gaseous pollutants that are indicative of primary emissions (CO, NO_x) or secondary atmospheric processing of precursors (O₃), and standard meteorological parameters (ambient temperature, relative humidity, atmospheric pressure).</p>
<p>Description: An MSNs' system integrates sensing, communication and power supply modules. All modules are included in an environmental enclosure with a high Ingress Protection (IP) rating to ensure continuous unattended operation, even during inclement weather conditions and in dust-laden environments.</p> <p>PM sensing is performed following the optical particle counting (OPC) principle. In OPC measurements, air is drawn in the PM sensor using a fan and led to a detection chamber (ideally in a straight-line path to avoid deposition losses of coarse particles inside the sensor), where particles scatter monochromatic light emitted by a laser source at various angles. A photodiode measures the amount of scattered light over time. The signal is converted to voltage pulses to calculate the number and size of passing particles concurrently. Single particles are counted and classified in multiple-size bins starting at circa 300 nm. Particle number concentrations are converted to PM mass concentrations, assuming spherical particles and using reference particle</p>

densities. Concentration data are provided by size category, allowing the concurrent determination of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁ on a continuous, near-real-time basis.

Measurement of gaseous pollutants is conducted by electrochemical sensing. Each sensor is sensitive to one chemical compound or group of compounds. The sensor comprises an electrochemical cell with 3 - 4 electrodes. Ambient air passively diffuses to the main working electrode. Due to the presence of gas, an electrochemical reaction is initiated in the cell, and the generated ions diffuse through a membrane to the counter electrode, where a voltage proportional to the gas measured is produced. A reference electrode is used to ensure that constant voltage is recorded at the working electrode and an additional auxiliary electrode, not exposed to air, can be frequently used for temperature compensation.

Meteorological sensing is carried out by an all-in-one miniaturised sensor. Meteorological measurements are useful for adjusting sensor measurements for thermal and hygroscopic interferences.

Due to the many sensing modules and auxiliary devices necessary to accommodate the various pollutant measurements and their uncertainties, it was considered optimal to power the MSN units through mains electricity and not solar (given the diverse insolation patterns expected in the CiROCCO pilot sites).

Most MSN systems transmit their data via LTE, providing the necessary throughput and independence from transmission distance limitations and landline availability (such as in cases of Wi-Fi, LoRa, and BTE). LTE coverage has been ensured at selected locations of all pilots (see deliverable D4.1). Data collected are stored in proprietary cloud-based platforms, through which they can be secondarily downloaded or re-transmitted through Rest API.

TRL:

9

Technology stack:

for measurements

- active air sampling
- straight-line particle induction
- laser radiation scattering
- optical particle counting in multiple size ranges
- state-of-the-art electrochemical gas sensing
- ozone filtration in nitrogen dioxide measurements
- meteorological sensing

for data collection and processing

- concurrent recordings of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁ concentrations
- process (in electrochemical cells) and post-hoc (data processing) temperature compensation for electrochemical sensors
- near-real-time data processing and transmission (resolution: ≤ 15 minutes)

for data transmission

- LTE network

for user interaction with the device

- REST API protocol for data transmission to the CiROCCO data streaming and management platform).

Dependencies with other components:

Input data:

- calibration equation parameters
- method detection limits
- upper threshold for valid measurements

will be entered into the CiROCCO data streaming and management platform after raw data is transmitted.

Output data:

Processed calibrated data after applying calibration models and Quality Assurance and Quality Control (QA/QC) procedures will be stored in the data management platform and displayed through the visualisation service. The processed data will also be fed to developed algorithms for the improvement of low-cost sensor outputs for PM and meteorological parameters.

Requirements:**Availability:**

MSNs will be operating continuously once installed and for a two-year period for which data processing and transmission licenses will be purchased by their vendor. After two years, internal pollutant sensors should be replaced, as they have an operational life and after this period, they will display concentration drifts and their performance will deteriorate.

Latency:

MSNs will provide data at a resolution of 15 minutes or less (depending on the API module that will be ultimately selected). Data aggregation will be done on an hourly basis in the platform.

Monitoring:

The validity of measurements should be checked every two days (routine check) in the platform. Data quality checks shall be performed every two weeks by NOA and pilot leaders. Further data processing and reporting will be decided in due course.

Extensibility & Scalability:

A single version of the MSN systems is foreseen by the CiROCCO proposal and allocated budget.

Security:

Access to data in the platform should be provided to registered CiROCCO system users with credentials.

Portability:

The MSN devices are portable as they do not weigh more than 10 kg but are not intended for portable / mobile measurements. They will be permanently installed at a location and provide stationary measurements. If a location change is necessary (e.g. due to issues with power or network connectivity, or due to localised emissions / factors affecting the representativity of concentrations), the new location will be first assessed by NOA and EBOS.

Deployment:

All four pilot site locations

Relevant WP:

WP3

Tasks:

Task 3.3

Involved partners:

NOA

Table 6: Portable sunphotometers

Component:
Portable sunphotometers
ID:
ISM-3
Purpose:

Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) is a quantitative dimensionless measure of the sunlight attenuation caused by atmospheric particles, either by scattering or absorption. The AOD measurements refer to attenuation caused by the total columnar aerosol load. The term Aerosol Optical Thickness (AOT) is often used interchangeably with AOD, though it is specified that AOD refers to the optical thickness due to aerosols measured vertically. Atmospheric optical thickness values can be increased by the presence of gases (e.g. O₃), and various aerosol types like water droplets, ice crystals, smoke particles from combustion and dust particles. AOD data retrieved by measurements, remote sensing observations and simulations are crucial in atmospheric science, as they represent aerosol optical properties and their potential impacts on the radiative budget, the climate in general, and even visibility and air quality.

A global network of automated state-of-the-art stations, the Aerosol Robotic Network (AERONET¹), measuring aerosol optical and radiative properties using high-end instrumentation (sunphotometers) has been established by National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), Photométrie pour le Traitement Opérationnel de Normalisation Satellitaire (PHOTONS), Université de Lille, Centre national d'études spatiales (CNES), Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS). However, its coverage in remote areas is limited and the equipment, calibration and operational costs are high. Alternatives through medium-cost portable monitors have been available for a long time. Recent technological advances have also provided low-cost handheld solutions. These instruments, which, due to their low cost (€ 1000 or lower), can be made available in large numbers, can be easily transported to various locations in the field and improve the spatial resolution of AOD measurements.

Ground-based AOD measurements in CiROCCO are essential for the assimilation of the dust modelling simulations (Task 3.4 | Satellite modelling and assimilation algorithm with the in-situ sensors). Such data are needed in all pilot sites, especially in the dust-source area of Egypt. Multiple locations representing different grid cells in the model should be included in the design. Therefore, a low-cost solution is necessary to allow for multiple-location measurements. Moreover, the handheld device features (small dimensions, low weight, battery operation) and associated ease of use and data retrieval will facilitate its operation by the non-specialised personnel that will be called up to undertake the task in the pilot areas.

Description:

The portable sunphotometer measures solar radiation intensity in multiple wavelengths of the visible region in the electromagnetic spectrum (blue, green and red bands). Based on a Beer-

¹ <https://aeronet.gsfc.nasa.gov/>

Lambert law equation and using reference and calibration data for the equation constants and parameters, the AOD value can be derived. The measurement in multiple wavelengths facilitates the calculation of Ångström coefficients that can be used in the identification of aerosol type (source, size and indirectly chemical composition).

The instrument provides direct data display, facilitating solar sighting and tracking of peak intensity measurements by the user. The optical thickness values are also displayed so that the user can verify the validity of the measurement. The portable device is equipped with a Global Positioning System (GPS) receiver to record its position and also measures meteorological parameters (e.g. atmospheric pressure) necessary for calculating conversion parameters.

Multiple measurements should be performed through the daylight period, representing different sun elevations and solar intensities. They will be conducted in both dust source and receptor areas. Field evaluation of the portable sunphotometer performance will be performed at an Cimel-equipped AERONET station in Greece, prior to their transport to the pilot areas.

TRL:

9

Technology stack:

for measurements

- solar radiation sensor-based measurement (optical-voltametric)
- concurrent multi-wavelength monitoring
- collimator for solar sighting

for data collection and processing

- GPS position logging
- scientific software for data processing and calibration using AERONET data

for data transmission

- Universal Serial Bus (USB) communication for data retrieval

for user interaction with the device

- touch display.

Dependencies with other components:

Input data:

- raw digital input measurements
- solar zenith angle
- atmospheric pressure
- calibration parameters for the calculation of optical thickness in the three wavelengths
- calibration parameters to adjust for the ozone contribution (green and red bands) to optical thickness.

The manufacturer provides the initial set of calibration parameters. For applications requiring GPS coverage, more detailed calibration approaches will be examined.

Output data:

- AOD measurements at three wavelengths
 - Ångström coefficients (value and reliability index) for aerosol typing
 - measurement date / time
 - solar elevation
 - GPS longitude and latitude
 - temperature and atmospheric pressure.
-

Measurements are taken three times daily, during the daylight hours. The data will be directly provided for the needs of the data assimilation component of Task 3.4 | Satellite modelling and assimilation algorithm with the in-situ sensors. After the end of the campaigns and necessary data filtering and processing, data will be uploaded to the platform. Both level 1.0 and level 1.5 data will be compiled.

Requirements:

Availability:

The portable sunphotometers will be operated on a campaign basis. Intensive campaigns of monthly duration will be conducted in the pilot areas during the Mediterranean dust period. Measurements will be uploaded to the data management platform after the finalisation of the campaigns and post-hoc data processing.

Resolution & Latency:

Measurements will be taken every day, three times a day, for a period of one month (the same time every day, excluding cases of cloudiness, when the time will be shifted accordingly). Measurements will not be transmitted online to the platform but offline at the end of the campaigns after the necessary QA/QC and processing.

Monitoring:

The user will screen the validity of each measurement. NOA will perform data quality checks two times a week to identify potential data quality issues in a timely manner. These procedures will be performed offline, and a logbook will be compiled.

Extensibility & scalability:

A single version of the portable sunphotometer will be used in the CiROCCO project.

Security:

Direct access to data will be provided for the needs of Task 3.4 | Satellite modelling and assimilation algorithm with the in-situ sensors. Once the data is migrated to the data management platform, access should be provided to registered CiROCCO users with credentials.

Portability:

The handheld sunphotometers are highly portable. They operate on rechargeable dry-cell batteries; their maximum dimension is smaller than 0.5 m, and their weight is lower than 1 kg. Mobile measurements with near real-time retrieval are also possible but will not be required in CiROCCO pilots. A wide operation temperature range (up to 50°C) will make possible the collection of data in the challenging conditions of CiROCCO pilot sites. The devices can be operated by a single user. They communicate through USB with a personal computer for the download and inspection of data. The locations in which measurements will be performed will be predefined before their transport to the measurement area.

Deployment:

All four pilot site locations

Relevant WP:

WP3

Tasks:

Task 3.3

Involved partners:

NOA

Table 7: High-end instrument for reference PM monitoring

Component:

High-end instrument for reference PM monitoring

ID:

ISM-4

Purpose:

Monitoring of atmospheric dust is one of the most crucial parameters in CiROCCO as the project targets desert or dust-impacted areas. Dust particles are categorised in the coarse aerosol range, meaning that their diameters typically exceed $1\ \mu\text{m}$, while their vast majority are larger than $2.5\ \mu\text{m}$. This suggests that dust particles are mostly represented by the PM_{10} regulatory metric, and their concentrations are strongly correlated with the $\text{PM}_{10}-\text{PM}_{2.5}$ difference. The $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ metric can also be affected by dust during episodic conditions related to extreme local emission or transport of dust particles (in the Mediterranean, this is mostly related to Saharan outbreaks). The PM_1 fraction is considered relatively impervious to dust.

Monitoring coarse dust particles using low-cost PM sensors is rather challenging. Due to the miniaturisation of sensors, particles are required to perform abrupt turns in the internal sampling-detection path, which results in coarse particles being deposited on the walls. Moreover, there are coincidence effects during the counting of larger particles. Therefore, the vast majority of low-cost PM sensors cannot monitor PM_{10} , and also return erroneous $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ measurements during the prevalence of dust conditions (when substantial quantities of dust particles permeate the fine particle range). Along with the LCSN systems of the CiROCCO system, a high-end PM sensor will be employed, which uses straight line sampling to avoid depositional losses and has advanced optics for the detection of particles in a large number of size ranges. However, all PM low-cost sensors are expected to face biases, which can also be related to particle hygroscopicity and sensor response to very high concentrations. Therefore, the reliability of PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ measurements must be assessed through comparison with a reference PM monitoring instrument.

CiROCCO sensors will be tested, evaluated and calibrated in Athens, Greece against reference PM monitors, before they are transported to the pilot areas. However, the conditions in the calibration area are different than those expected in the CiROCCO fields of measurement, and therefore the performance of the LCSN for PM and especially dust measurements should be re-verified by in-situ comparative measurements with a monitor that is standardised according to standards of Comité Européen de Normalisation (CEN) / International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO). The quality of PM and especially coarse particle measurements is crucial in CiROCCO as these data will be used for the validation of the satellite modelling datasets of Task 3.4 | Satellite modelling and assimilation algorithms with in-situ sensors.

For this purpose, once deployed in the pilot areas, a standalone reference PM monitor that can continuously record PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ concentrations will be collocated with LCSN sensors to evaluate their performance in actual conditions and make any needed data adjustments.

Description:

Reference monitoring in the EU has been carried out according to the provisions of the EN 12341:1998 (PM₁₀) and EN 14907:2005 standards (PM_{2.5}). There are various continuous PM monitors that provide data in hourly resolution or less and have been certified for reference-equivalence with the standards. Certification of such automated PM instruments (e.g. beta attenuation monitors) is provided according to the EN 16450:2017 standard (Automated measuring systems for the measurement of the concentration of particulate matter (PM₁₀; PM_{2.5})). However, these traditional reference-equivalent instruments typically measure only one of the two parameters, incurring high costs for the characterisation of coarse particles (multiple monitors with different sampling heads).

Recent technological advances have made available the reference-equivalent measurement of both regulated PM metrics concurrently by a single instrument while also providing valuable information on the particle mass and number size distributions of Total Suspended Particles (TSPs) in numerous size ranges. Such instruments rely on the OPC technology that has been described earlier for the medium-cost sensing nodes, albeit in a larger number of size channels, starting at lower diameters (0.2 µm or even less) and using very advanced optics for single particle detection. Moreover, these reference-equivalent OPC counters perform controlled drying in the incoming particle stream to prevent water condensation that affects the particle size distributions and, in turn, the determined PM concentrations.

In the CiROCCO project, a reference-equivalent PM monitor will be used for the reverification of LCSN node performance through collocated measurements in the pilot areas. Most reference-equivalent PM monitors are rack-mounted instruments and require an existing station infrastructure (e.g. container-type) with a vertical sampling line. Since such infrastructure will not be available in the remote areas of the CiROCCO pilots, there is a need for the instrument to be placed in a suitable compact environmental enclosure that will permit its operation in the outdoor environment. Given the high temperatures (exceeding 40°C) anticipated in some of the pilots (e.g. in southern Egypt), this enclosure should be air-conditioned to ensure the reliable operation of the monitor and the reference-equivalence of the measurements. A meteorological sensor is typically supplied to monitor temperature, relative humidity and atmospheric pressure.

Once the LCSN networks have been deployed, measurement using the high-end systems will be performed for 2 – 4 weeks in the pilot areas. These instruments are capable of unattended operation and data collection. Once installed by the local personnel, regular audits will be required to ensure the continuation of their operation.

Technology stack:

for measurements:

- pump-assisted active air sampling with regulated flow
- vertical inlet with controlled adaptive heating for condensation control
- laser radiation scattering
- optical single particle counting in multiple size ranges (> 16 channels per decade)
- PSL-traceable particle sizing
- concurrent recording of PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, PM₁, PM(coarse) and TSP concentrations
- reference-equivalent monitoring for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} (QAL1 certification)
- meteorological sensing
- weatherproof air-conditioned environmental enclosure with digital temperature control.

for data transmission

-
- communication through USB, serial and Ethernet interfaces
 - data logging with capability to transmit data over Global System for Mobile communications (GSM).

for user interaction with the device

- touch display.

Dependencies with other components:

Input data:

- volumetric flow rate
- ambient temperature and atmospheric pressure

are measured and logged continuously by the instrument.

Output data:

- particle mass size distribution (TSP, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, PM₁, PM_{coarse})
- particle number size distribution.

The output data storage interval is selectable and ranges at least from one minute to one hour. Data will not be transmitted online to the platform but collected and processed after the conclusion of each campaign. The data will be directly provided for the needs of Tasks 3.3 | Data pre-processing and synchronisation of different accuracy sensing nodes and Task 3.4 | Satellite modelling and assimilation algorithm with the in-situ sensors. After the end of the campaigns and necessary data filtering and processing, data will be uploaded to the platform. New adjustment factors for the measurements of LCSN and MSN systems, determined by the comparisons with the high-end systems, will be entered into the platform if needed.

Requirements:

Availability:

The high-end reference PM monitor will be operated on a campaign basis. Intensive campaigns of 2 – 4-week duration will be conducted in the pilot areas (four sequential campaigns due to the availability of one instrument), after the deployment of the LSN networks. The timing of these campaigns is related to the deployment of the networks and transportation considerations. Collected measurements will be uploaded to the platform after the finalisation of the campaigns and post-hoc data processing.

Latency & resolution:

High-end monitors will record data locally at a one-minute resolution. Measurements will not be transmitted online to the platform but offline at the end of the campaigns after the necessary QA/QC and processing. Data aggregation will be done offline on an hourly and daily basis.

Monitoring:

Local personnel at the pilot areas will check the monitors' operation every 2 - 3 days (routine audits). Maintenance will be performed each time the instrument returns from the pilot sites to the NOA facilities. This will include cleaning the inlet nozzle and sampling head, checking flow rate and zero, and checking meteorological sensors.

Extensibility & Scalability:

A single version of the high-end PM monitor will be used in the CiROCCO project.

Security:

Direct access to reference PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} and other monitored data (including TSP and particle size distributions) will be directly provided for the needs of Tasks 3.3 and 3.4. Once the data is migrated to the platform, access should be provided to registered CiROCCO users with credentials.

Portability:

The PM monitor along with its environmental enclosure will weigh more than 100 kg and the larger dimension of the enclosure will be up to or exceed 1 m. Therefore, the system is not portable. It will be transported to the monitoring sites as freight, by road, ship or aircraft. Assembly and set-up of the system by the local personnel of the pilots will be required – following detailed instructions that will be provided by NOA. The device should be placed at a location where it will be collocated with LCSN systems and, if possible, with an MSN system. Mains electricity will be required on site. The weatherproof air-conditioned environmental enclosure will permit standalone operation in outdoor conditions.

Deployment:

All four pilot site locations

Relevant WP:

WP3

Tasks:

Task 3.3

Involved partners:

NOA

3.3.2. Aerosol data assimilation

Table 8: Aerosol data assimilation component

Component:

Aerosol data assimilation

ID:

ADA-1

Purpose:

Aerosol assimilation refers to the process of integrating observational data on aerosol fields forecasted by atmospheric models. Within the CiROCCO project, a process for assimilating observations on modelled desert dust fields has been developed. This assimilation process addresses several purposes, including enhancing atmospheric models, leading to improved air quality monitoring and a better scientific understanding of the spatial and temporal distribution of desert dust and its related environmental impacts.

Description:

Within the framework of Task 3.4 | Satellite modelling and assimilation algorithms with in-situ sensors with duration from M10 to M28 of the CiROCCO project, NOA is responsible for providing satellite remote sensing components, particularly pertaining to the estimation of dust optical depth (DOD). This estimation will be achieved through the utilisation of satellite DOD products, such as ModIs Dust AeroSol (MIDAS), a global fine-resolution DOD data set (Gkikas et al., 2021). The MIDAS dataset will be assimilated, by using a Newtonian relaxation approach specifically adapted for dust-related data (Pejanovic et al., 2010). This method has previously been employed for assimilating the

ECMWF MODIS dust product (Pejanovic et al., 2012) and the MSG-SEVIRI DOD (Solomos et al., 2017). In addition to the MIDAS dataset, measurements of AOD on desert dust-dominated cases will also be used for the assimilation. These AOD measurements will be collected using portable sunphotometers (ISM-3 component of the CiROCCO system) in the pilot regions, namely low-cost AOD measurements will be carried out. It should be noted that since LiDAR climatology of vertical aerosol structure for space-based lidar simulation studies (LIVAS), a 3D multi-wavelength aerosol / cloud dataset based on CALIPSO and EARLINET data (Amiridis et al., 2015) is no longer available due to the CALIPSO satellite data discontinuity (the end of CALIPSO science mission was on 1 August 2023), no LIVAS data will be assimilated, contrary to the initial proposal.

For the aerosol data assimilation, two different model outputs are produced:

- model forecasts prior to the assimilation of the observations, namely MIDAS DOD and low-cost AOD data, named forecast data, and
- model outputs after data assimilation, named analysis data.

Following aerosol data assimilation, both forecast and analysis data will be evaluated against data gathered from LCSNs in the pilot areas.

Assimilating MIDAS DOD and medium-cost AOD data will involve applying the procedure depicted in Figure 4, on selected past dates to attain a solution that minimises disparities between background fields, namely the initial results of simulations using the Weather Research and Forecasting model coupled with chemistry (WRF/Chem atmospheric model²) and observations (MIDAS DOD and medium-cost AOD data) within a specified assimilation window. Subsequently, the assimilated fields, referred to as dust analyses, will be assessed using PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ data derived from LCSNs (ISM-1 component). Various standard evaluation statistical metrics, including bias, root mean square error, and mean absolute error, will be computed to gauge the performance of the assimilated fields.

The different components of the aerosol data assimilation that will be developed within the CiROCCO project are depicted below and include: forecast data, assimilation module, MIDAS dataset, data from portable sunphotometers, analysis data, and data from LCSNs.

Figure 4: Flowchart of the aerosol data assimilation procedure.

² <https://ruc.noaa.gov/wrf/wrf-chem/>

Technology stack:

for data assimilation

The aerosol data assimilation procedure relies on:

- WRF/Chem model and specifically, the Advanced Research Weather version of the Weather Research and Forecasting model (WRF-ARW), version 4.5.1. The WRF-ARW model is coupled with chemistry (WRF/Chem, Skamarock et al., 2021; Grell et al., 2005) and simulates the emission, transport, and mixing of aerosols simultaneously with the meteorology feedback. It has been used in several studies to examine dust transport and the implications of dust in clouds (Drakaki et al., 2022; Marinou et al., 2021). In WRF-Chem, the meteorological core of the WRF-ARW model is coupled with the Goddard Chemistry Aerosol Radiation and Transport (GOCART) model. The GOCART model, coupled with the Air Force Weather Agency (AFWA) dust emission scheme (LeGrand et al., 2019), simulates mineral dust and sea salt aerosols (SSA). The WRF/Chem code is written in Fortran.
- assimilation module which uses the MIDAS dataset and the WRF/Chem forecasts for the assimilation of the DOD is written in Python.
- module with the evaluation codes for the analysis.

for data processing

The implementation of the assimilation procedure, which includes WRF/Chem model simulations, runs with the assimilation model, and the outputs' evaluation, will be performed on NOAA's computer cluster. The data assimilation module, coded in Python and including bash scripts, is under development. This procedure also requires the execution of atmospheric simulations, which will be carried out on NOAA's computer cluster.

for data transfer

NOAA's File Transfer Protocol (FTP) server will be used for the transfer of input and output data from aerosol data assimilation to the data streaming and management platform (STMV-1 component) and directly to the early warning system (MP-1 component).

for data storage

After completion of aerosol data assimilation, the following data will be transferred for storage to the data streaming and management platform (STMV-1 component):

- MIDAS dataset
- forecast data
- analysis data.

Dependencies with other components:

Input data:

- low-cost AOD data from portable sunphotometers (ISM-3 component)
- air quality measurements from LCSNs (ISM-1 component)

on the availability of aerosol data on which assimilation depends. Both datasets are required before applying the assimilation procedure and should cover the same time period. The first data set is needed for the implementation of the data assimilation procedure, while the second data set is needed for the subsequent assessment of the results.

Requirements:

Availability:

The aerosol data assimilation component is not and will not be operational within the framework of the CiROCCO project and works as a database of the MIDAS dataset, model forecast and analysis data provided by Task 3.4 once after the completion of the Task 3.4.

Spatial and temporal resolution:

An equal-distance grid is utilised with the WRF/Chem model with a spatial grid spacing of 12 km × 12 km consisting of 420 × 301 points. In the vertical direction, 31 vertical sigma pressure levels of up to 50 hPa are utilised. The simulation period consists of daily 96-h forecast runs, which are initialised at 12:00 UTC. Additionally, from each 94-h run, the first 12 h are discarded as are the model-spin up period.

Deployment:

NOA computer cluster

Relevant WP:

WP3

Task:

T3.4

Deliverable:

D3.4

Involved partners:

NOA

3.3.3. Data stream transfer, management and visualisation

Table 9: Nanosatellite IoT network

Component:

Satellite IoT network

ID:

STMV-1

Purpose:

The satellite IoT communication service is useful in areas without terrestrial communication. This service will enable LCSNs developed in the context of the CiROCCO project to be deployed in almost any location on Earth. However, in the duration of the CiROCCO project, due to availability of terrestrial network in all the pilot areas it is not necessary to use this ASTRO service. However, to demonstrate the performance of the technology, project partners have concluded on the implementation of one node with ASTRO technology at one pilot area.

Description:

Figure 5: Pictorial diagram of the operation of ASTRO's nanosatellite IoT network

Figure 5 above shows the operation of the service provided by ASTRO. Astronode S is the ASTRO communication module which is implemented in sensor node. It collects data and transmits that to satellites when the satellites enter the field of view of the module.

The ASTRO relies on a constellation of Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites. The nanosatellites in LEO orbit over the entire globe and, therefore, they are not always present in the field of view of the Astronode S module. This means that the data remain temporarily stored in the buffer until Astronode S modules detects a nanosatellite.

A ground station is used to receive the collected sensor data from nanosatellites. The nanosatellite should enter field of view of the ground station to transmit the data back to Earth. This means that the ASTRO service has inherent latency, and this latency depends on the number of nanosatellites operational in the constellation at any given time.

Once the data has been transferred from the ground station to the data management platform, then it can be fetched through the ASTRO Application Programming Interface (API) and used with any application. It should be noted that, as each satellite is in the field of view of an Astronode S module for a limited amount of time, the total amount of data that can be transferred daily is limited.

To use the ASTRO service, the sensor node should integrate Astronode S as a communication module. To simplify the integration, Astronode S+ boards can be used which includes Astronode S with a patch antenna. By only connecting few wires to power up the Astronode S+ and Universal Asynchronous Receiver / Transmitter (UART) communication, the Astronode S+ module could be easily integrated into any sensor node.

The peak power consumption of the Astronode S module during transmitter mode is about 350 mW. The module includes different power management modes to optimise the power consumption for supporting battery-powered applications. Additionally, the device enters sleep mode automatically when the satellites are not in the field of view.

Technology stack:

for operation:

- in house designed, built and operated constellation of nanosatellites
- KSAT and Leaf Space ground stations

for data transmission:

- proprietary wireless communication protocol (co-developed with Airbus) in L-band to transfer the sensor data to the satellites

- Application Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) developed with CEA is used in Astronode S modules to communicate with the nanosatellites in the most power efficient way

for data storage and distribution

- Azure cloud-based data platform hosting ASTRO's databases, portal and API as well as for supporting data processing.

Dependencies with other components:

Input data:

Data collected by LCSNs to be transmitted by the Astronode S module.

Output data:

Data initially collected by LCSNs are provided by through ASTRO's API and portal for use to the various CIROCCO system components and services.

Requirements:

Availability:

ASTRO's nanosatellite IoT network provides a communication service for any region around the globe and is particularly suitable for regions without terrestrial any network coverage.

Latency:

< 18h

Monitoring:

The provision of ASTRO's service is monitored to ensure continuously transmission of data.

Extensibility & Scalability:

ASTRO's service is easy scalable as multiple sensor nodes can be deployed across different locations at the same time and data collected could be transmitted for the desired application.

Security:

Role-based access controls are enabled. Access to asset data is managed by end-user per use case requirements.

Portability:

The Astronode S module can be embedded in any product.

Deployment:

Pilot 4 in Spain

Relevant WP:

WP3

Task:

T3.2

Involved partners:

ASTRO

Table 10: Data streaming and management platform

Component:

Data streaming and management platform

ID:

STMV-2

Purpose:

One of the main goals of the CiROCCO project is to establish a robust, scalable, and safe platform capable of streaming, processing, and storing data. Towards this goal, the platform design and implementation need to be scalable so that it can be extended and interact with multiple and different sensing nodes and with the services expected to be provided at the four pilot areas.

Description :

Figure 6 : Pictorial diagram of INTRA’s data streaming and management platform

As part of Task 3.5 | Data integration and data management platform, INTRA will configure the Streamhandler platform to seamlessly integrate sensing, simulation, testing and validation data sources into data processing components. Streamhandler is a high-performance distributed platform based on Apache Kafka that handles real-time data. As depicted in Figure 6 above, it can ingest and handle massive amounts of data into processing pipelines for both real-time and batch-processing. The deployment of the Streamhandler platform may span multiple virtual machines, providing all the necessary technologies for storage and analysis of data as well as the usage of technology agnostic algorithms by offering a distributed computing environment that will support big data calculations, modelling, optimisation, parallelisation and uncertainty quantification.

Technology pack:

for data transfer:

The main connection between LCSNs and the platform is achieved through the Message Queing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol, a standard lightweight protocol for IoT messaging. Data collected by sensing nodes are communicated through a REST API from private cloud infrastructure to the data streaming and management platform. Data can also be retrieved from the platform through a dedicated REST API for services designed to be provided in the CiROCCO pilot areas.

for operation:

The entire data streaming and management platform will be deployed on the cloud and more specifically, the Hetzner cloud servers.

for data storage:

For the deployment of the data management platform to cover the needs of the CiROCCO project in terms of data storage, InfluxDB has been selected as the most suitable. This open-source database that is designed for managing time series data is supported by the data streaming and management platform.

for operations monitoring:

A custom admin dashboard has been developed using JavaScript and specifically, the React library. The programming language Python will be used to add all necessary backend feature of the data streaming and management platform.

for interaction with the platform:

- custom admin dashboard for the visualisation of imported data
- Grafana dashboard
- UI for the time series database.

Dependencies with other components:

Input data:

- LCSNs measurements
- medium-cost sensor measurements retrieved from private cloud infrastructure through dedicated API
- portable sunphotometer measurements
- sensor data transferred through the nanosatellite IoT network and retrieved through ASTRO's API
- forecast and analysis data from the aerosol data assimilation component

Output data:

- data visualised on the platform's admin dashboard
- data provided for the visualisation service
- data retrieved for the CiROCCO services to be deployed in four pilot areas.

Requirements:

Availability:

The data streaming and management platform will be operational all the time. It has proven fault tolerance, resiliency to node failures and supports automatic recovery.

Latency:

The Streamhandler component of the data streaming and management platform can accommodate near real-time data transfer.

Monitoring:

There is an inherent mechanism for monitoring the seamless functionality of the data streaming and management platform and logging keeping to understand its behaviour and spot issues.

Extensibility & scalability:

The data streaming and management platform with all its components will be deployed for the CiROCCO pilot studies. Nonetheless, the platform is highly scalable and able to accommodate any increased needs that may arise with future upgrades to the network of sensors and services to be provided in pilot areas.

Security:

- encryption and secure communication with the platform using the Hypertext Transfer protocol secure (HTTPS) protocol
- authenticated access to the platform’s messaging and data storage components
- firewall protection of the platform, checking and filtering input data based on a set of security rules.

Deployment:

Hertzner cloud infrastructure managed by INTRA

Relevant WP:

WP3

Task:

T3.5

Deliverable:

D3.5

Involved partners:

INTRA

Table 11: Data visualisation service

Component:
Data visualisation service

ID:
STMV-2

Purpose:
This visualisation component of the CiROCCO system aims to facilitate the visualisation of measurements collected from CIROCCO sensor nodes deployed in the four pilot areas in Cyprus, Egypt, Serbia, and Spain. The service will provide interactive and dynamic dashboards to display real-time data visualisations of all monitored parameters.

Description:
The main functionalities of the CiROCCO visualisation service are as follows:

- provision of overview information associated with each CIROCCO pilot and parameters under consideration
- time-series and map-based visualisations of monitored parameters, while offering support for aggregated visualisations
- advanced filtering capabilities allowing to focus on data placed on certain locations or areas, or on data taken within specified time frames
- giving different background illustrations of the area
- provision of guidance for how the user can interact with the service
- giving option to users to visualise the content given in various languages.

Figure 7: CiROCCO visualisation service's components

The visualisation service involves the following components, depicted in Figure 7:

for input

- Streamhandler API for retrieving data from in situ sensors

for processing

- data ingestion service for parsing, validating, and transforming (i.e. processing) data for storage

for storage

- TimescaleDB with PostGIS to securely store large volumes of spatiotemporal data, which supports advanced geospatial queries

for processing

- data filtering and aggregation component, where data are extracted, filtered, and aggregated as well as prepared for visualisation

for output

- visualisation platform where data are presented with interactive and dynamic dashboards that display real-time data visualisations needed for easy user understanding.

Technology stack:

The **development** of the CiROCCO visualisation service will be based on Flutter, an open-source UI software development kit created by Google. It is primarily used for building natively compiled applications for mobile, web, and desktop from a single codebase. Flutter has gained popularity due to its flexibility, efficiency, and the rich set of features it offers for developing visualisation services.

Dependencies with other components:

The CiROCCO visualisation service relies on the data streaming and management API to access real-time sensor data from various sources. The accuracy and completeness of the visualisations that can be produced by this service are heavily dependent on the data collected and retrieved through this API.

Requirements:

Availability: The CiROCCO visualisation service will be highly available to allow continuous access to real-time data visualisations. Redundancy measures will be in place to prevent data loss and reduce service interruptions to minimal.

Extensibility & scalability: The visualisation service will allow the integration of additional features and functionalities in the future, such as new visualisation types or user interaction methods and additional new data sources, if needed. The service will also be able to scale horizontally to serve increasing number of requests, ensuring good performance as the demand grows.

Security: Data encryption will be enforced (using HTTPS) to protect user data and sensor information. In addition, user authentication, and access control will be applied to protect sensitive data using industry standards for security including Open Authorisation (OAuth) 2.0 and OpenID Connect.

Deployment::

All the components of the CiROCCO visualisation service will be containerised and deployed on Kubernetes (K8s). The K8s will be deployed on-premises on top of a highly available proxmox cluster.

Relevant WP:

WP3

Involved partners:

ICCS

3.3.4. CiROCCO pilot systems

Table 12: Solar energy production nowcasting and forecasting

Component:
Solar energy production nowcasting and forecasting
ID:
PL-1
Purpose:
The CiROCCO's solar energy production nowcasting and forecasting component is considered to facilitate the planning of renewable energy production systems in Benban Solar Park and its expansion beyond the Pilot 1 area in the Egypt region. It will set the ground for a virtual representation of the real energy pilot system, i.e. a digital twin for solar energy applications.
Description:
The solar energy production nowcasting and forecasting component will be tasked with the harmonisation of model simulations with in-situ measurements as well as real energy production data from the power plant in the Pilot 1 area.
The data processing chain will cover a combination of Earth Observation (EO) and in situ data and will rely on methods for working with real-life data. EO data consists of satellite observations. In addition to EO data and in-situ measurements, model simulations will also be used, while the real-life data will be representative of the Benban Solar Park real energy production levels (Figure 8).
All EO will be incorporated into the virtual model, which will act as a digital twin of the real energy production system. Once this harmonisation will have been completed, then the holistic planning of an energy production system will be tested on an operational basis at the Pilot 1 site.
Finally, an expansion to the whole Egyptian region will be deployed as a first step towards the development of a robust decision support application for solar energy production planning and management purposes.

Figure 8: Pictorial diagram of the energy production nowcasting and forecasting component structure

Technology stack:

The core system deployment will rely on computer vision and AI algorithms, radiative transfer and numerical weather prediction models, and

for high-performance computing:

- the cloud processing infrastructure of Amazon Web Services

for operational running:

- C++ and Bash programming languages

for interaction with the service:

- GeoServer UI.

Dependencies with other components:

Input data:

- Copernicus and Eumetsat data for aerosol and cloud optical properties and microphysics
- in-situ atmospheric data for temperature, solar irradiation, wind direction / speed and aerosol levels
- real-life photovoltaic energy production data from Benban solar park

Output data:

- simulated and forecasted solar irradiation and energy levels produced operationally in real-time.

Requirements:

Availability:

The solar energy production nowcasting and forecasting component will run operationally and in real-time providing new data every 15 minutes including the solar irradiation and energy levels at the current time and as historical chart from 6 hours back to 6 hours ahead at 15-minute intervals.

Monitoring:

The continuous monitoring of solar energy production levels will require the synchronous data provision and auto-harmonisation between the simulations, the in-site measurements and the real energy production flows from the Benban solar park.

Extensibility & scalability:

The first modelling processing chain will include the Benban solar park digital twin for energy production applications, while an expansion for the whole Egyptian region will be also demonstrated as a follow-up processing alternative without the ground-truth data. The proposed method will be totally transferable / replicable into any location following the in-situ sensors deployment logic and the combination with its digital twin for solar energy production applications.

Deployment:

Pilot 1

Relevant WP:

WP4

Task:

T4.2

Involved partners:

CEDARE, NOA

Table 13: Desert Dust Storm (DDS) early warning system

Component: DDS early warning system
ID: PL-2

Purpose:

The early warning system within the CiROCCO project addresses frequent DDS events occurring in Cyprus, which contribute significantly to air quality exceedances (10% - 40%). DDS events pose substantial public health risks, particularly to vulnerable populations such as children, the elderly, and individuals with pre-existing health conditions, causing respiratory and cardiovascular issues.

Surveys in Eastern Mediterranean countries, including Cyprus, have identified gaps in action plans for DDS events. The early warning system aims to provide accurate and timely forecasts to enable proactive public health measures. Current models often underestimate DDS intensity due to insufficient meteorological and soil data. The early warning system will improve forecasting accuracy by incorporating detailed meteorological and particle data, particularly in desert-adjacent areas lacking in-situ stations.

A pilot study³ in the Municipality of Idalion will enhance the early warning system capabilities by refining DDS forecasts, especially for regions with high anthropogenic pollution. This system update is crucial for mitigating DDS impacts on public health and the environment.

Description:

³ For further details, refer to the CiROCCO deliverable D4.1 | Planning and setup handbook, and operational management report - initial

The early warning system aims to enhance the prediction and management of DDS events in Cyprus. It provides timely and accurate forecasts to mitigate the adverse effects on public health and the environment. The early warning system collects real-time data from high-end sensor nodes and LCSNs, processes this data to calculate time-averaged values, and offers options for calculating hourly and daily averages. This data is visualised through an interactive dashboard that includes time series plots, descriptive statistics, and configurable notifications for air quality conditions. These features enable authorities and the public to take timely and appropriate actions during DDS events.

As depicted in the Figure 9, the system will integrate external data sources via APIs, including data from the Air Quality Monitoring Network of the Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance, operational predictions from the Barcelona Dust Regional Center portal using the NOA WRF/Chem model, and simulated data with assimilations from the NOA FTP server using the NOA WRF/Chem model.

Using secure communication protocols, raw data can be retrieved by both internal and external sources, ensuring the early warning system can operate within the CiROCCO system as well as independently. This capability enhances the system's utility in broader research and public health initiatives, aiming to reduce the adverse impacts of DDS events on both the population and the environment.

In the Municipality of Idalion, a pilot study aims to enhance the early warning system's capabilities by improving its forecasting accuracy by considering meteorological conditions and particle properties. This will provide a technical update necessary to protect the public effectively in an area with significant anthropogenic sources.

Figure 9: CiROCCO DDS early warning system architecture design

Technology stack:

The early warning system will utilise an advanced and comprehensive technology stack designed for effective operation and seamless integration with other system components. This technology stack will encompass the following elements:

for data retrieval

REST APIs will be employed to facilitate secure data exchange with external sources. These APIs will integrate data from various sources, including the Air Quality Monitoring Network of the Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance, satellite tools, and products under the Copernicus observation programme and the EC-ESA initiative. The APIs will ensure secure and efficient data transfer, adhering to standard communication protocols like HTTPS for encrypted communication and OAuth for secure user authentication. The early warning system will use REST APIs to provide a

standardised method for accessing and integrating diverse datasets, enabling real-time data retrieval and updates.

for data storage and management:

A cloud-based SQL database system, designed to handle high-resolution real-time air quality and meteorological data, will provide robust support for structured data, complex queries, and transactions, ensuring the reliable management of large volumes of data generated by the sensing nodes and other input sources. This system will support scalable storage solutions and flexible data schemas to efficiently store, query, and analyse the extensive datasets required for accurate and timely forecasts. Using SQL ensures data integrity, consistency, and the ability to perform advanced analytics, which are critical for the dynamic and varied nature of environmental monitoring data.

for the system development

The software development for the EWS will be based on Python to ensure robust functionality and efficient data handling. Python was chosen for its extensive libraries and frameworks, which are suitable for data processing, analysis, and machine learning, making it ideal for managing large datasets and performing complex computations required by the early warning system. Additionally, Python's versatility and readability facilitate quick development and maintenance of the system. Using Python ensures a consistent development environment and leverages its strengths in scientific computing and data visualisation, essential for the dynamic and varied nature of environmental monitoring data.

for operation

The processing infrastructure for the early warning system will utilise a local development cluster to handle data processing tasks efficiently. The local development cluster will be responsible for initial data validation, preprocessing, and testing to ensure data quality before integration. This setup provides a scalable and flexible infrastructure capable of managing real-time data effectively. By focusing on a local development cluster, the early warning system ensures low latency, high performance, and the ability to quickly adapt to changing processing needs. This infrastructure will support the computation of real-time averages and statistical values, ensuring timely and accurate data analysis.

for interaction with the system

The UI for the early warning system will include a dashboard designed to provide internal users with interactive visualisations and comprehensive data summaries. This dashboard will offer features such as interactive time series plots, where users can define the duration and time resolution of the data displayed. It will also provide descriptive statistical values (mean, median, max, min, percentile values) and configurable notifications through a traffic light system indicating air quality conditions (e.g. green for low, yellow for moderate, orange or high, red for very high pollution levels). Registered users will have varying authorisation levels to access this information.

Dependencies with other components:

Input data:

The early warning system highly depends on various data sources and interfaces, both within the CiROCCO system and external entities. Key dependencies include real-time data input from high-end sensing nodes and LCSNs deployed across strategic locations within the Municipality of Idalio. These nodes will monitor various environmental factors such as air temperature, atmospheric pressure, air humidity, sand / soil temperature, wind direction, wind speed, solar radiation, ozone levels, and particulate matter concentrations (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀). The system will integrate data from the existing Air Quality Monitoring Network of the Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance and operational predictions from the NOAA WRF/Chem model, focusing on the grid cell of the Idalio

area to ensure accurate forecasting of DDS events. Simulated data with assimilations from the NOA server and satellite tools will further enrich the input dataset, enhancing the precision of predictions.

Output data:

The early warning system will output secure raw data retrieval capabilities for both external and internal users. This data will be formatted to facilitate easy visualisation and post-processing, ensuring that users can effectively utilise the information for various analytical purposes. Internally, the early warning system will provide a dashboard offering interactive visualisations and comprehensive statistical summaries. The dashboard will feature interactive time series plots where users can define the duration and time resolution, allowing for flexible and detailed analysis of air quality data. Additionally, it will present descriptive statistical values such as mean, median, maximum, minimum, and percentile values, providing users with an in-depth understanding of the data. Configurable notifications will be implemented through a traffic light system categorising air quality conditions into levels. This system will ensure that users are promptly alerted to significant changes in air quality. Registered users will have access to this information with varying authorisation levels, ensuring that data security and user privacy are maintained. High-level users such as researchers and municipal authorities will have more comprehensive access and control over the data and system settings, while general users may have more limited view-only access.

Requirements:

Availability:

The EWS component is designed to ensure continuous operation, providing real-time monitoring and timely alerts regarding DDS events. The system will include robust disaster recovery mechanisms to maintain data integrity and service availability during potential failures or disruptions. These mechanisms will involve regular data backups, redundancy in critical system components, and failover strategies to ensure that the system remains functional even under adverse conditions. By incorporating these features, the early warning system will be able to guarantee high availability and reliability.

Latency:

The early warning system is designed to deliver data, measurements, and forecasts with minimal latency to ensure timely response to DDS events. The system aims to provide updates at hourly-level granularity, ideally offering new data and forecasts every hour. This high-frequency data collection and processing are essential for accurately predicting and responding to DDS events in real-time. The low latency requirements will necessitate the use of efficient data processing algorithms, high-speed communication networks, and optimised data storage solutions to handle the large volumes of data generated by the sensing nodes and other input sources.

Monitoring:

Continuous and automated monitoring of the early warning system will be essential to ensure it functions as expected and provides accurate data. The system should implement automated monitoring tools that check its operation every three hours, verifying data accuracy, system performance, and sensing node connectivity. These monitoring tools should generate alerts in case of any anomalies or failures, enabling prompt corrective actions. Additionally, periodic manual inspections and maintenance checks should be conducted to ensure the system's long-term reliability and performance.

Extensibility & Scalability:

The design of the early warning system is focused on real-time data collection and basic statistical analysis, with a structure that supports future enhancements. Extensibility will be a key requirement, allowing the system to incorporate additional functionalities such as advanced predictive modelling, integration of new data sources, and improved UIs in future versions. Scalability will also be critical, as the system needs to accommodate an increasing number of sensing nodes and data streams without compromising performance. The early warning system is designed with modular components and scalable infrastructure, enabling it to handle growing data volumes and computational demands as the system expands

Security:

Security is a top concern, given the sensitivity of the data and the need to protect user privacy. The system must implement robust security measures, including role-based access controls to ensure that only authorised users can access sensitive information or configure system settings. Data encryption will be used to protect data during transmission and storage, and secure communication protocols (such as HTTPS) will be employed to prevent unauthorised access. Regular security audits and vulnerability assessments will be conducted to identify and address potential security threats.

Deployment:

Pilot 2

Relevant WP:

WP4

Task:

T4.3

Involved partners:

UCY

Table 14: Land use and ecosystem management system

Component:

Land use and ecosystem management system

ID:

PL-3

Purpose:

The primary purpose of the land use and ecosystem management system will be to provide support for operative short-term and mid-term drought and wildfire risk assessment, as well as to support long-term forest management ecological planning in the Deliblato protected natural area. This vulnerable region faces increasing threats from climate change, including wildfires, droughts, extreme weather events and other complex interactions of natural and anthropogenic influences. The challenging environmental conditions make continuous field measurements difficult and costly. By combining data from the innovative and accessible CiROCCO system, remote sensing products from the Copernicus Sentinel missions, and field surveys, the system will enable high-resolution, near-real-time ecological mapping. This will help identify vulnerable areas and apply timely mitigation measures.

Description:

The land use and ecosystem management system will comprise of the following four subcomponents:

The **in-situ data processing and visualisation** component retrieving data from the CiROCCO sensing nodes network will be crucial for real-time wildfire risk and air quality assessment, application of

timely mitigation measures and issuing warnings. The continuous measurement of the most important meteorological parameters, together with soil moisture and air quality indicators, also provide the basis for studying longer-term trends and interactions needed for reforestation and forest preservation planning. The measurements will also serve to verify and calibrate EO remote sensing products, especially land surface temperature, moisture, soil moisture and vegetation quality estimates.

The **EO processing and visualisation** component uses primarily data from Copernicus Sentinel 1 and Sentinel 2 missions. The images will be obtained through API calls from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem and will be further processed to provide soil moisture estimates (from Sentinel 1 and 2) and assessments of vegetation state (Sentinel multispectral vegetation and moisture indices). The system will allow the ingestion of other available EO products as well.

The third component with **geospatial data** will be created from datasets on topography, soil, periodic detailed land use / land cover, forest stand and vegetation surveys.

The fourth component will involve **integration of modelled data**: short-term meteorological forecasts (produced by deep learning and graph neural networks), long-term climate models, soil moisture and dynamic vegetation models, and will be essential for the predictive functions of the system.

Figure 10: Land use and ecosystem management system structure

Technology stack:

for data management and storage:

The land use and ecosystem management system will utilise an ArcGIS server combined with Environmental Systems Research Institute (ESRI) geodatabase for geospatial data management. The ArcGIS server will be used for hosting, sharing, and real-time analysis of spatial data. The ESRI geodatabase will serve as the primary storage for handling various data types including vector, raster, and tabular data. This integration will allow for advanced spatial analysis, high-resolution mapping, and secure data management, enabling robust support for environmental monitoring, risk assessment, and long-term ecological planning in the Deliblato natural area. The interconnection of local server with the CiROCCO data streaming and management platform will be achieved via REST API calls.

for the system development:

The land use and ecosystem management system will be based in Python for data acquisition, processing, and visualisation. Python's extensive libraries and frameworks facilitate efficient data handling and analysis. Custom scripts will be developed to automate the extraction and processing of data from various sources, including in-situ sensors and remote sensing products. This processed data will be then visualised through dynamic, interactive plots and maps, ensuring efficient monitoring and analysis functions. The flexibility of the Python environment will ensure that the system can adapt to evolving data needs for ecological monitoring and management.

for interaction with the system:

Access for system users will be provided through a web application with interactive web mapping and basic data visualisation functions.

Dependencies with other components:

Input data:

- Copernicus Sentinel 2 L2A multispectral images of the region of interest, filtered for cloud cover (single data point size: up to 20MB GeoTIFF with Lempel–Ziv–Welch (LZW) compression / observation every 3 - 6 days)
- Copernicus Sentinel 1 data (single data point: up to 20 MB / every 3 - 4 days, processed datasets)
- in-situ data from the CiROCCO sensing nodes
- high-resolution digital elevation model (single GeoTIFF file with LZW compression, up to 400 MB)
- soil maps
- forest stand maps
- land use / land cover maps

Output data:

- processed multispectral indices map
- drought risk map
- wildfire risk map
- ecological status and vulnerability map.

Requirements:

Availability & disaster recovery:

The land use and ecosystem management system is being designed to ensure uninterrupted operation through advanced availability and disaster recovery mechanisms. Continuous real-time monitoring will supported by a robust infrastructure that includes data backup management, multidirectional component connectivity and redundant system components. These measures will be implemented to preserve data integrity and maintain service functionality during potential

disruptions or failures. This approach will guarantee that the system remains operational and reliable, providing consistent ecological monitoring and timely alerts.

Latency:

The system will be designed to deliver timely and accurate data with minimal latency. In-situ measurements will be carried out every 60 minutes, ensuring real-time monitoring of critical parameters such as soil moisture, temperature, wind speed and air quality. The system will generate daily updates on drought and fire risk, providing essential information for immediate decision-making and risk mitigation. Additionally, a comprehensive ecological status report will be produced monthly, providing a detailed overview of long-term trends and ecosystem health. This structured data delivery schedule will ensure that stakeholders receive the most current and relevant information, enabling effective management of the Deliblato protected natural area.

Monitoring:

The system should include continuous and automated monitoring protocols to ensure data accuracy and integrity. Data integrity checks, and connectivity verification should be performed after every data measurement and transmission cycle (i.e. one hour). In case of detected anomalies, automated notification should be sent about the problem to system administrators.

Extensibility & scalability:

The initial version of the system is being designed to integrate in-situ measurements from the CiROCCO system, EO and other relevant geospatial data from models and surveys related to the Deliblato sands special nature reserve. The architecture of the system will allow integration of additional input data.

Deployment:

Pilot 3

Relevant WP:

WP4

Task:

T4.4

Involved partners:

INO, VSUME

Table 15: Modelling GHG exchanges and PM emissions

<p>Component: Modelling GHG exchanges and PM emissions</p>
<p>ID: PL-4</p>
<p>Purpose: The CiROCCO’s GHG exchange and PM emissions modelling component is considered to deduce the source and behaviour of aerosol particle exchanges and discriminating near from far sources in “Balsa Blanca”-and “Llano de los Juanes”, the two areas of interest within in the Almeria Province where Pilot 4 site is located, as presented in deliverable D2.2.</p>
<p>Description: The GHG exchange and PM emissions modelling component of the CiROCCO system will comprise of the following components to collect data for improving the spatial resolution of predictions of GHG exchanges and PM emissions and also evaluations of the predictions:</p> <p>Flux-tower eddy covariance (FTEC) station equipped with infrared gas analyser to measure CO₂ and H₂O densities, a sonic anemometer to measure wind speed and temperature, and a data logger to</p>

record and process data. Additional instrumentation measures meteorological, soil, vegetation and vadose zone parameters, including CH₄, CO₂, and H₂O.

High-quality stand-alone electronic sensing nodes installed in close proximity to the existing infrastructure to measure target parameters of the CiROCCO project, namely air and soil temperature, wind speed, humidity, amount and distribution of precipitation, O₃, solar radiation, aerosols, and PM.

Multiple LCSNs deployed around each high-quality stand-alone electronic sensing node in the areas of interest, which will measure the same parameters as the high-end nodes.

Bidimensional modelling of GHG exchanges and particle emissions, while considering radiative transfer modelling using dust forecast models, e.g. DREAM (Damiano et al., 2022).

Dependencies with other components:

Input data:

- in-situ measurements from the CIROCCO LCSNs and high-quality sensing nodes

Output data:

- simulated and forecasted aerosol

Deployment:

Pilot 4

Relevant WP:

WP4

Task:

T4.5

Involved partners:

CSIC

4. Process viewpoint of the platform

In this section, the process view of the system is included. By sequence diagrams are documented the way the data will follow per pilot case, in order to be uploaded to the data management platform, having as an entry point each project available sensor, and as final result, the expected output of each pilot use case.

4.1. Interconnections between system components

The table below presents all the communication points between the CiROCCO components. For readability purposes, the components are presented in the table below by their ID, as they are defined in Section 3. To note that the orange cells refer to the internal components of the CiROCCO system, and the grey ones refer to the external databases that provide data to the system components.

Table 16: Interconnections between system’s components.

ID	ISM-01	ISM-02	ISM-03	ISM-04	ADA	STMV-01	STMV-02	STMV-03	PL-01	PL-02	PL-03	PL-04	EXT-01	EXT-02	EXT-03	EXT-04	EXT-05
ISM-01						↑	↑										
ISM-02							↑										
ISM-03							↑										
ISM-04							↑										
ADA							↑↓										↓
STMV-01	↓						↑										
STMV-02	↓	↓	↓	↓	↑↓	↓		↑	↑	↑	↑	↑					
STMV-03							↓										
PL-01							↓						↓				↓
PL-02							↓						↓	↓	↓		
PL-03							↓						↓				
PL-04							↓										
EXT-01									↑	↑	↑						
EXT-02										↑							
EXT-03										↑							
EXT-04																	
EXT-05									↑								

4.2. Pilot 1 | Renewable energy systems planning in Egypt

Pilot 1, located in Egypt, focuses on renewable energy production management and planning by using sensor and remote sensing data collected in the Bendan solar power plan with an advanced modelling infrastructure. Towards this aim, LCSNs and high-end nodes will be deployed to collect solar radiation measurements, wind speed and direction, particulate matter measurements along with temperature and humidity data that will be used as input in conjunction with satellite observations for real-time dust monitoring and assimilation and importantly, for obtaining high-resolution solar irradiation estimations.

4.2.1. Sequence diagram for Pilot 1

The sequence diagram in Figure 11 presents the interactions between components involved in renewable energy production planning and management. It presents the data flow from the various sensing nodes through Streamhandler to the data management platform and from there, along with the data from the external databases to the model harmonisation component, which then provides the expected output for supporting the operational management of the solar plant through the dedicated UI.

Figure 11: Sequence diagram for pilot 1 in Egypt

4.3. Pilot 2 | Desert dust storm events monitoring in Cyprus

Pilot 2, located in Cyprus, focused on monitoring and forecasting DDS events which contribute adversely to air quality. Towards this goal, LCSNs and high-end monitoring sensors will be deployed to collect measurements necessary for enhancing the existing early warning system for DDS events and fine tune forecasting models.

4.3.1. Sequence diagram for Pilot 2

The sequence diagram in the following Figure 12 details the interactions and processes involved in the early warning system for monitoring DDS events in Cyprus, as part of pilot 2 of the CiROCCO project. This diagram represents the flow of data starting with the initial collection of measurements by the various sensing nodes, through the raw data processing component and the component for forecasting DDS based one simulation models, to the final dissemination of alerts and data visualisations for end-

users. Each step highlights the critical components involved and their interactions, ensuring timely and accurate monitoring and response to DDS events.

Figure 12: Data flow for the DDS early warning system

In

Pilot 2 - Desert dust storm events monitoring in Cyprus

Figure 13 below the interactions among the early warning system components and processes involved are depicted from a technical point of view. This sequence diagram presents the data flow from multiple different sensing nodes and the external databases to a central data processing component, and then to the next components through which insights and forecasts are presented to the end user.

Pilot 2 - Desert dust storm events monitoring in Cyprus

Figure 13: Sequence diagram for pilot 2 in Cyprus

4.4. Pilot 3 | Sustainable environmental restoration support in Serbia

Pilot 3 located in Serbia focuses on the environmental monitoring and supporting ecosystem management in Deliblato Sands, which is increasingly susceptible to land degradation and wildfires by climate change-induced extreme weather events. Towards this goal, LCSNs will be deployed to provide local stakeholders with access to near real-time information through the land use and ecosystem management system under development.

4.4.1. Sequence diagram for Pilot 3

The diagram in

Pilot 3 - Sustainable environmental restoration support in Serbia

Figure 14 shows the information flow from the sensing nodes to the end user. As it can be seen, the central component in the data flow for the pilot 3 of the CiROCCO system is the land use and ecosystem management system. It is the central point for all the systems’ outputs, as it has as input raw data from the sensing nodes, external databases (Copernicus Sentinel 1 & 2), the geospatial data and the forecasts from the model component. The output will be shared through a dedicated dashboard.

Figure 14: Sequence diagram for Pilot 3 in Serbia

4.5. Pilot 4 | Modelling greenhouse gases (GHG) and particle emissions in Spain

Pilot 4 that is located in the South of Spain focuses on modelling GHG exchanges and PM emissions, particularly those related to DDS events and forecasting how their cycles could affect air and water quality in the future. Towards this goal, LCSNs will be deployed to support the existing infrastructure for monitoring atmospheric variables, to collect data of higher spatial and temporal resolution and ultimately, to enhance the forecasting ability of models.

4.5.1. Sequence diagram for Pilot 4

Figure 15 below presents the interactions between the different components of the system for pilot 4. This pilot case has an interesting particularity because of the integration of satellite communications for the transfer of measurement data between LCSNs and the data management platform. Except for the standard internet communication from the sensing nodes to the Streamhandler platform, in this case, the LCSNs support the communication with the Astrocast satellites, and from the Astrocast portal, the data are ingested into the CiROCCO platform through a REST API.

Pilot 4 - Modelling Green House Gases and particle emissions in Spain

Figure 15: Sequence diagram for Pilot 4 in Spain

5. CiROCCO system deployment viewpoint

Based on the methodology analysed in Section 2, development diagram presents the physical architecture of the CiROCCO system platform. The primary role of the diagram is to provide a clear view of the system's nodes for deployment and maintenance purposes. Furthermore, it depicts the hardware and software components configuration across CiROCCO's components and the overall system communication between the respective nodes.

Figure 16 below presents an overall deployment diagram of the entire CiROCCO system deployments across the identified infrastructure. It illustrates in depth how the system is composed and how the software and hardware infrastructure is configured.

Figure 16: CiROCCO's system deployment diagram

The following Figures 17 to 20 present the deployment diagrams for the configuration of the CiROCCO system for each pilot case. All diagram depicts the communication between each pilot server and the CiROCCO core system as well as the interactions with external components of the CiROCCO system (Copernicus, EC-ESA, etc.).

Figure 17: Deployment diagram for Pilot 1 in Egypt

Figure 18: Deployment diagram for Pilot 2 in Cyprus

Figure 19: Deployment diagram for Pilot 3 in Serbia

Figure 20: Deployment diagram for Pilot 4 in Spain

6. Conclusions

In this deliverable, the outcomes of activities carried out under Task 2.3 have been presented. More specifically, the design of the architecture for the CiROCCO system has been presented. Interfaces, data flows, component interactions, logical views, process views, deployment views and the methodology used have been thoroughly analysed. In addition, the specifications of the logical structure of the CiROCCO system architecture, focusing on the interconnections among the discrete components have been provided. The components developed in the context of the CiROCCO project were also specified.

7. References

- Amiridis, V., Marinou, E., Tsekeri, A., Wandinger, U., Schwarz, A., Giannakaki, E., Mamouri, R., Kokkalis, P., Biniotoglou, I., Solomos, S., Herekakis, T., Kazadzis, S., Gerasopoulos, E., Proestakis, E., Kottas, M., Balis, D., Papayannis, A., Kontoes, C., Kourtidis, K., Papagiannopoulos, N., Mona, L., Pappalardo, G., Le Rille, O., and Ansmann, A. (2015) LIVAS: a 3-D multi-wavelength aerosol/cloud database based on CALIPSO and EARLINET, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 15, 7127–7153, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-15-7127-2015>
- Damiano, R., Sannino, A., Amoroso, S., and Boselli, A. (2022) Aerosol characterization with long-term AERONET sun-photometer measurements in the Naples Mediterranean Area, *Atmosphere*, 13, 2078, <https://doi.org/10.3390/atmos13122078>
- Drakaki, E., Amiridis, V., Tsekeri, A., Gkikas, A., Proestakis, E., Mallios, S., Solomos, S., Spyrou, C., Marinou, E., Ryder, C. L., Bouris, D., and Katsafados, P. (2022) Modeling coarse and giant desert dust particles, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 22, 12727–12748, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-12727-2022>
- Gkikas, A., Proestakis, E., Amiridis, V., Kazadzis, S., Di Tomaso, E., Tsekeri, A., Marinou, E., Hatzianastassiou, N., and Pérez García-Pando, C (2021) ModIs Dust AeroSol (MIDAS): a global fine-resolution dust optical depth data set, *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, 14, 309–334, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-14-309-2021>
- Grell, G. A., Peckham, S. E., Schmitz, R., McKeen, S. A., Frost, G., Skamarock, W. C., and Eder, B. (2005) Fully coupled “online” chemistry within the WRF model, *Atmospheric Environment*, 39, 6957–6975, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2005.04.027>
- Kruchten, P. B. (1995) The 4+1 view model of architecture, *IEEE Software*, 12(6), 42-50, <https://doi.org/10.1109/52.469759>
- LeGrand, S. L., Polashenski, C., Letcher, T. W., Creighton, G. A., Peckham, S. E., and Cetola, J. D. (2019) The AFWA dust emission scheme for the GOCART aerosol model in WRF-Chem v3.8.1, *Geoscientific Model Development*, 12, 131–166, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-12-131-2019>
- Marinou, E., Voudouri, K. A., Tsikoudi, I., Drakaki, E., Tsekeri, A., Rosoldi, M., Ene, D., Baars, H., O’Connor, E., Amiridis, V., and Meleti, C. (2021) Geometrical and Microphysical Properties of Clouds Formed in the Presence of Dust above the Eastern Mediterranean, *Remote Sensing*, 13, 5001, <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13245001>
- Skamarock, W. C., Klemp, J. B., Dudhia, J., Gill, D. O., Liu, Z., Berner, J., Wang, W., Powers, J. G., Duda, M. G., Barker, D., and Huang, X. -yu. (2021). *A Description of the Advanced Research WRF Model Version 4.3* (No. NCAR/TN-556+STR), <https://doi.org/10.5065/1dfh-6p97>